

The effect of RADEC learning model (read, answer, discuss, explain, and create), school environment, and motivation on learning outcomes of students in grade vii in social studies subjects in MTS Negeri 2 Kotamobagu

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Abstract

One of the factors that can improve student learning outcomes is a good learning model, the school environment and also the student's own learning motivation. Students do not improve their learning outcomes if the learning model is not interesting, the use of a good learning model in the teaching and learning process is expected to attract students' attention to enthusiasm in receiving lessons. The learning model is also a form of problem solving that stimulates student motivation to learn, also supported by a good school environment can also encourage students to obtain optimal learning outcomes. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of the RADEC Learning Model (Read, Answer, Discuss, Explain, And Create), School Environment, and Motivation on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in ips subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu. This research method uses a quantitative approach then testing the research hypothesis is done with a Structural Equation Model (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) and the number of respondents sampled in this study is the entire number of seventh grade students as many as 302 respondents. The results showed that the RADEC Learning Model (Read, Answer, Discuss, Explain, And Create), School Environment, and Motivation had an effect on student learning outcomes in class VII ips subjects. Teachers should understand and integrate the Radec learning model in every learning activity and encourage students to actively participate in learning. As well as providing constructive feedback related to student performance.

Keywords: RADEC (Read; Answer; Discuss; Explain; And Create) Learning Model; School Environment; Motivation; Learning Outcomes

1. Introduction

The 21st century is a century full of challenges and various changes, all fields must adapt to these changes including the field of education. Education is the key to the progress of a nation and the progress of a nation will be achieved if each of its citizens has the skills and knowledge needed to compete with others. Trianto (2010: 171) suggests that social studies is an integration of various branches of social sciences, such as sociology, history, geography, economics, politics, law and culture formulated on the basis of social realities and phenomena that embody an interdisciplinary approach from aspects and branches of these social sciences.

Social studies learning in schools should not be directed solely to prepare students to prepare students to continue to a higher level, but basically the purpose of social studies education is to educate and provide basic skills to students to develop themselves and be motivated according to their talents, interests, abilities, and environment as well as being able to solve problems faced in everyday life using the analytical concepts they learn at school, being able to make the right decisions using scientific concepts, and having a scientific attitude in solving the problems faced. However, the

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facts encountered in the field that learning outcomes, especially social studies at MTS Negeri 2 Kotamobagu, still show low scores.

Learning outcomes are the results or scores that students get from the evaluation results after the activity of the learning process. Learning outcomes are changes that occur in individuals who learn, not only changes regarding knowledge, but also the ability to form skills in behavior. Learning outcomes are the results achieved by students after the learning process in a certain time which is measured using certain evaluation tools.

These learning outcomes if associated with social studies learning outcomes can be shown by changes in behavior in students, both affective, cognitive, and psychomotor aspects. These changes occur after the social studies learning process carried out in the school environment and outside of school as measured by using measuring instruments in the form of tests and non-tests.

In the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 104 of 2014 concerning Assessment of Learning Outcomes by Educators, it is stated that learning outcomes assessment is the process of collecting information / evidence about the learning achievements of students in spiritual and social attitude competencies, knowledge competencies, and skill competencies carried out in a planned and systematic manner during and after the learning process. Learning outcomes are influenced by two factors, namely: factors that come from outside the student, namely social factors and non-social factors, and factors that come from within the student, namely psychological factors and physiological factors such as: ability, motivation to learn, results, attention, attitude, learning habits, perseverance, physical and psychological conditions (Hamalik, 2004: 30).

Although a person's learning outcomes can be influenced by various factors, what is very prominent is the dominant role of the teacher in the learning process at school. The learning pattern that is almost always done is the lecture method, which in the end is not optimal. To achieve optimal learning outcomes, many things must be addressed, including the selection of learning models that are appropriate to the subject matter so that they can stimulate student learning outcomes.

The use of a good learning model in the teaching and learning process is expected to attract students' attention to enthusiasm in receiving lessons. The learning model is also a form of problem solving that stimulates students' motivation to learn. In addition to stimulating learning motivation, it can also make it easier for students to understand the material being taught. The use of models in learning activities is very necessary to facilitate the learning process in order to obtain optimal learning outcomes. Without a clear learning model, the learning process will not be directed so that learning objectives are difficult to achieve. This learning model is very useful in the teaching and learning process in the classroom, both for teachers and students.

Based on the results of initial observations found by researchers, the most crucial problem is the low student learning outcomes in social studies subjects. This can be seen in the table of the acquisition of learning outcomes of social studies subjects in class VII MTS Negeri 2 Kotamobagu odd semester and even semester of the following school year:

Table 1 Average Report Card Score of MTS Negeri 2 Kotamobagu

Class	KKM	YEAR OF STUDY		
		2021/2022		2022/2023
		Odd Semester	Even Semester	Odd Semester
VII A	75	71,00	73,02	88,85
VII C	75	70,75	72,18	85,78
VII D	75	78,25	75,25	76,82
VII E	75	77,15	74,10	80,65
VII F	75	70,00	75,50	76,68
VII G	75	75,25	74,35	82,68
VII H	75	71,50	78,25	78,88

(Source: curriculum section of MTS Negeri Kotamobagu)

Based on the minimum completeness criteria (KKM), the average social studies report card score above illustrates that in general the ability of students in social studies subjects is still low. The low student learning outcomes, from the findings of researchers influenced by various factors. According to the researcher's conjecture that there are various influencing factors including: low student learning motivation, learning activities are still more dominated by the teacher in front of the class, the lack of teacher creativity in using learning models, learning media that are still limited so that not all classes can use the media for a long time, students are rarely involved in group assignments, so they tend to compete with each other in an unhealthy direction, limited learning support facilities in the school environment are not adequate to reach the needs of students.

In this study, researchers set three alternatives that will be used as independent variables in solving problems related to learning outcomes, namely learning models, motivation, and school environment. The learning model used in this study is the radec learning model. This learning model is a learning model that requires students to build critical thinking skills that are oriented towards mastery of competencies and skills. able to develop their potential so that they can become human beings who believe in God, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent and become democratic and responsible citizens.

According to Dalyono (2009, p. 59) the school environment can be interpreted as follows: The state of the school where it affects the level of learning success, the quality of the teacher, his teaching methods, the suitability of the curriculum to the child's abilities, the state of facilities or equipment at school, the implementation of school rules, and so on. All of this contributes to the success of the child.

In learning activities, motivation is needed to arouse students' passion for learning so that learning activities can run well. According to Sardiman (2018: 75) is "The overall driving force within students that gives rise to learning activities, which ensures the continuity of learning activities and provides direction to learning activities, so that the goals desired by the learning subject can be achieved".

Research Objectives

- To determine the effect of Radec Learning Model on the learning motivation of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu.
- To determine the effect of School Environment on the learning motivation of seventh grade students in social studies at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu
- To determine the effect of Radec Learning Model on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu
- To determine the effect of School Environment on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu
- To determine the effect of learning motivation on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu
- To determine the effect of Radec Learning Model through learning motivation on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu
- To determine the effect of School Environment through learning motivation on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu

2. Literature review

2.1. Student Learning Outcomes

Learning outcomes are the abilities or achievements of students that students achieve after going through the teaching and learning process. Sudjana (2011: 22) states that learning outcomes are the abilities that students have after they receive their learning experience.

2.2. RADEC Learning Model (Read, Answer, Discuss, Explain. And Create)

Sopandi (2017) explains, "The Read, Answer, Discuss, Explain And Create (RADEC) learning model is an alternative learning model that is in accordance with Indonesian conditions". According to Sopandi, et al (2019: 4), this learning model is a learning model that requires students to build critical thinking skills in the Indonesian context and aims to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe in God, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent and become democratic and responsible citizens.

2.3. School Environment

According to Sukmadinata (2009, p. 164) "The school environment plays an important role in the learning development of students". Meanwhile, according to Sabdullah (2010, p. 196) the school environment is as follows: School is an educational environment that is deliberately designed and implemented with strict rules such as having to be tiered and continuous, so it is called formal education and school is a special institution, a vehicle, or a place to organize education, in which there is a teaching and learning process to achieve certain educational goals.

2.4. Learning Motivation

Uno (2017: 23), says that learning motivation is an internal and external drive in students who are learning to make changes in behavior, generally with several indicators or elements that support. From several definitions of learning motivation according to the experts above, it can be concluded that learning motivation is an impetus that arises both from within and outside the student, which is able to generate enthusiasm and enthusiasm for learning and provide direction to learning activities so that the desired goals can be achieved.

2.5. Hypothesis

- H1 : It is suspected that there is an effect of the Radec Learning Model on the learning motivation of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu?
- H2 : It is suspected that there is an effect of school environment on the learning motivation of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu?
- H3 : It is suspected that there is an effect of Radec Learning Model on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu?
- H4 : It is suspected that there is an effect of school environment on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu?
- H5 : It is suspected that there is an effect of learning motivation on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu?
- H6 : It is suspected that there is an effect of Radec Learning Model through learning motivation on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu?
- H7 : It is suspected that there is an effect of school environment through learning motivation on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu?

3. Research methods

3.1. Types and Sources of Data

The type of data in the study when viewed from its source is primary data, namely data regarding the responses of seventh grade students at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu regarding the Radec learning model, school environment, motivation towards social studies subjects. The responses of these students were obtained through questionnaires and direct observation of all seventh grade students who were respondents in this study.

3.2. Data Collection Methods

3.2.1. Questionnaire Method

Questionnaire (statement list), to complete the data the author needs, in this case the author asks and submits a list of statements to be answered by the students.

3.2.2. Literature Research Method

The library research method, namely collecting data from various related literature sourced from books and theses and using internet services.

3.2.3. Sample Determination Method

According to Sujarweni and Endrayanto (2012: 13) say that, population is a generalization area consisting of objects / subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics set by researchers to study and then draw conclusions. The population in this study were all seventh grade students at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu below will describe the population data more clearly as follows:

Table 2 Total Research Population

No	Class	Number of students
1	VII A	35
2	VII B	38
3	VII C	39
4	VII D	39
5	VII E	38
6	VII F	37
7	VII G	39
8	VII H	37
Total		302

Source: School Statistics Data FY 2022/2023

3.2.4. Operational Definition of Research Variables

Conceptual definition is an element of research that explains the characteristics of a problem to be studied. While Operational is empirical research data, the concept must be operationalized by turning it into a variable or something that has value. The conceptual and operational definitions of variables are explained in table 3.2

Table 3 Conceptual and Operational Definitions

Research Variables	Conceptual Definition	Operational Definition	Indicator
X1 Radec Learning Model	The Radec (Read, Answer, Discuss, Explain, and Create) learning model is a learning model that uses its stages as the name of the model itself, namely Read or reading, Answer or answering, Discuss or discussing, Explain or explaining, and Create. Creat atau mencipta.	<p>1 Read/Read (R) means that learners read information from various sources such as books, newspapers, magazines, and the internet. At this stage students have been given pre-learning questions by the teacher, pre-learning questions are given by the teacher before the teaching and learning process in the classroom.</p> <p>2 Answer/Answer (A) which means that learners answer pre-learning questions that have been given by the teacher based on the knowledge they have gained in reading activities (R), pre-learning questions are prepared by the teacher in the form of Worksheets Learners' Guide (LKPD).</p> <p>3. Discuss (D) is where learners learn in groups to discuss the answers to the pre-learning questions. At this stage the teacher motivates learners to help each other who are having difficulty or have not mastered the material. At this stage the teacher must ensure that there is communication in the group during discussion activities and ensure that students are right to work according to the teacher's instructions.</p> <p>4 Explain (E) means that learners carry out presentation activities with one representative who masters the learning indicators or the designated group leader. At this stage the teacher must ensure that what is explained by students in front of the class is scientifically correct and other students pay attention and understand what is being explained, at</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve students' critical thinking skills. 2. Improve students' analyzing and reading skills. 3. Improve cooperation in groups. <p>Kaharuddin and Nining Hajeniati (2020: 123)</p>

		<p>this stage the teacher also encourages students to ask questions, refute, or add to what has been explained by students in front of the class.</p> <p>5. Create (C) means that the teacher trains students to be able to apply or use the knowledge they have mastered to produce creative ideas or thoughts. This step trains students to think critically, creatively and work together.</p>	
X2 School Environment	<p>The school environment is an educational environment that is deliberately designed and implemented with strict rules such as having to be tiered and continuous, so it is called education.</p> <p>formal and school is a special institution, a vehicle, a place to organize education, in which there is a teaching and learning process to achieve certain educational goals.</p>	<p>Teachers are educators who provide a number of knowledge to students. With the knowledge and skills they have, teachers can make students become smart and disciplined individuals.</p> <p>2. Learning infrastructure and facilities are factors that influence student learning motivation. The state of the school building and classrooms are neatly organized, the school library room yang teratur, The availability of classroom and laboratory facilities, the availability of textbooks, media/learning aids are important components to support learning activities.</p> <p>2. Building conditions Include good air ventilation, sunlight can enter, sufficient lighting, spacious classrooms, and sturdy building conditions. If the atmosphere of the room is dark, the room is cramped, there is no ventilation and the building is damaged, it will make the learning process less good so that it is possible for the learning process to be hampered. Seating arrangements include patterns in rows or rows of learning, group stacking patterns, horseshoe formation patterns, and circular or square patterns. From the above opinion, it can be concluded that the indicators of the school environment in this study are teacher-student relationships, student-student relationships, student learning spaces and places, classroom facilities, learning tools, school libraries as learning support, classroom ventilation and classroom lighting.</p>	<p>1. Teacher 2. Facilities and Infrastructure 3. Building condition Tu'u (2004: 18)</p>
X3 Learning Motivation	<p>learning motivation is an impetus that arises both from within and outside the student, which is able to generate enthusiasm and enthusiasm for learning and provide direction to learning activities so that the desired goals can be achieved.</p>	<p>The existence of rewards in learning The existence of verbal statements such as praise or other awards for good behavior and good student learning results is an easy and effective way to increase student learning motivation.</p> <p>Interesting activities in learning Simulations and games are one of the interesting activities in learning. An interesting atmosphere causes the learning process to be meaningful, which will always be remembered and understood. With interesting activities It can also motivate and excites students to learn so that students become active in class.</p> <p>The existence of a conducive learning environment, so that it allows a student to learn well. A conducive learning environment is everything related to the place where the learning process is carried out which is appropriate and supports the continuity of the learning process. With a conducive learning environment such as a clean, neatly organized, quiet,</p>	<p>Adanya penghargaan dalam belajar Adanya kegiatan yang menarik dalam belajar Adanya lingkungan belajar yang kondusif Uno (2011:23)</p>

		comfortable classroom atmosphere and so on, it can arouse student learning motivation and keep students focused on learning.	
Y Learning Outcome	Learning outcomes are changes obtained by students after experiencing learning activities. The changes obtained depend on what the student learns. The success of a person in the teaching and learning process is mostly measured by measuring instruments of learning tests, which are given at the end of learning or at the end of the semester.	Cognitive domain, including knowledge, understanding, application, assessment, creation, and evaluation. The effective domain, including acceptance, responding, and determining values. Psychomotor domain, including fundamental movement, generic movement, ordinative movement, creative movement.	1.Cognitive domain. 2.Effective domain. 3.Psychomotor domain. (in Ricardo & Meilani, 2017).

4. Analysis Method

4.1. Validity Test

This test consists of validity and reliability. The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. The validity test criteria are If, $r_{count} > r_{table}$ means Valid. The results of testing the validity of the variables can be seen as follows:

Table 4 Validity Testing Results

No	Variable X1		Variable X2		Variable Z		Variable Y	
	rcount	Status	rcount	Status	rcount	Status	rcount	Status
1	0.368	Valid	0.502	Valid	0.492	Valid	0.491	Valid
2	0.701	Valid	0.569	Valid	0.392	Valid	0.628	Valid
3	0.619	Valid	0.655	Valid	0.456	Valid	0.519	Valid
4	0.674	Valid	0.664	Valid	0.374	Valid	0.817	Valid
5	0.767	Valid	0.734	Valid	0.716	Valid	0.631	Valid
6	0.558	Valid	0.641	Valid	0.719	Valid	0.603	Valid
7	0.717	Valid	0.809	Valid	0.701	Valid	0.688	Valid
8	0.533	Valid	0.696	Valid	0.650	Valid	0.420	Valid
9	0.539	Valid	0.755	Valid	0.741	Valid	0.640	Valid
10	0.667	Valid	0.521	Valid	0.644	Valid	0.751	Valid
11	0.615	Valid	0.662	Valid	0.490	Valid	0.718	Valid
12	0.644	Valid	0.421	Valid	0.702	Valid	0.373	Valid
13	0.631	Valid	0.520	Valid	0.808	Valid	0.792	Valid
14	0.504	Valid	0.501	Valid	0.717	Valid	0.792	Valid
15	0.533	Valid	0.759	Valid	0.826	Valid	0.430	Valid
16	-	-	0.657	Valid	0.708	Valid	0.533	Valid

17	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.569	Valid
18	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.445	Valid

Source: SPSS 21 Data Processing, 3024

4.2. Reliability Test

Decision making based on Cronbach's alpha value if the alpha value exceeds or is equal to 0.6 then the variable statement is reliable and vice versa (Ghozali, 3016). The results of the reliability test for each variable can be seen as follows:

Table 5 Reliability Testing Results

No	Variables	Reliability Results	Standard	Status
1	Radec learning model	0,873	0.6	Reliable
2	School environment	0,893	0.6	Reliable
3	Learning motivation	0,885	0.6	Reliable
4	Learning outcomes	0,883	0.6	Reliable

Source: SPSS 21 Data Processing, 3024

5. Results

5.1. Variant Analysis (R2) and Determination Test

The path coefficient evaluation is used to show how strong the effect or influence of the independent variable is on the dependent variable. While the coefficient determination (R-Square) is used to measure, how much endogenous variables are influenced by other variables. The results of the analysis regarding the level of R Square for the entire equation are presented in the form of the following figure:

Figure 1 PLS Algorithm

Based on the picture above, the overall R Square results can be described as follows:

Table 6 R Square Results

No.	Variables	Variable Z	Variable Y		Total Indirect Effect	
			Direct (L)	Indirect (TL)	L+TL	Increase
1	Radec learning model	0,709	0,364	0,203	0,567	35,80%
2	School environment	0,178	0,168	0,051	0,219	23,29%
3	Learning motivation		0,286			
Simultaneous Determination		0,672	0,532			29,55%

Source: PLS processed, 2024

5.2. Hypothesis Testing

Based on the data processing that has been done, the results can be used to answer the hypothesis in this study. Hypothesis testing in this study was carried out by looking at the T-Statistics value and the P-Values value. The results of hypothesis testing in the form of structural equations can be presented in the following figure:

Figure 2 Hypothesis Testing Results

Based on the picture above, the results of hypothesis testing can be described. The research hypothesis can be declared accepted if the P-Values value < 0.05 .

6. Discussion

6.1. The effect of the Radek learning model on the learning motivation of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu

The results of descriptive testing found that the overall percentage of the achievement score for the Radek learning model variable was 84.80% which was in the "good" category. This shows that seventh grade students of MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu feel that the Radek learning model has been implemented by teachers so far well with the hope of improving the effective learning process and learning outcomes in accordance with the set targets. although in the good category, there is still a need to optimize 2 aspects, namely Read and Answer which are the basis for implementing the Radek learning model in seventh grade students in social studies subjects.

6.2. The influence of school environment on the learning motivation of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu

The results of descriptive testing found that the overall percentage of the achievement score for the school environment variable was 84.19% which was in the "good" category. This shows that class VII students of MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu feel the existence of a school environment that can stimulate a good learning process and good learning outcomes as well. The school environment will tend to encourage students to be able to carry out various learning activities comfortably, safely and peacefully so that it will have an impact on the achievement of various targets in learning. Although in good condition, the school environment still needs to be optimized, especially regarding the condition of the school building from MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu. Improving and optimizing the condition of the school building also involves the involvement of various parties, including the school, local government, and the surrounding community. It takes good coordination to design and implement school infrastructure improvements, ensuring that facilities such as classrooms, libraries, toilets, and sports areas meet safety and comfort standards.

6.3. The effect of the Radek learning model on improving the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu

A learning model is a systematic framework or approach used to design and manage the learning process in order to achieve educational goals. Learning models provide a structure for teachers or facilitators to deliver learning materials and guide interactions between students and teaching materials. Learning models can include a variety of strategies, techniques and methods designed to facilitate students' understanding, retention and application of knowledge. The RADEC learning model is one alternative learning model that is suitable for Indonesian conditions (Sopandi, 2017).

6.4. The influence of the school environment on improving the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu

The school environment can be defined as the physical and social context in which the educational process takes place. It includes all aspects that influence students' learning experiences and contribute to the overall atmosphere in educational institutions. The school environment not only includes physical buildings such as classrooms, corridors and sports facilities, but also involves social aspects such as the relationships between students, teachers and school staff.

6.5. The effect of learning motivation on improving the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu

The results of descriptive testing regarding learning motivation found that the overall percentage of achievement scores for learning motivation variables was 78.78% which was in the "Good Enough" category. This shows that class VII students of MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu have a fairly optimal learning motivation in order to implement an effective learning process and progressive learning outcomes. High motivation from students comes from internal and external aspects which will certainly encourage students to be more enthusiastic in learning and doing assignments as VII grade students of MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu. All indicators of learning motivation must continue to be optimized so that students are better at achieving optimal learning outcomes.

The results of descriptive testing of learning outcomes found that the overall percentage of achievement scores for learning outcomes variables was 76.91% which was in the "Good Enough" category. This shows that students in grade VII MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu tend to still have to optimize the learning outcomes of social studies subjects because of the 3 indicators, cognitive and psychomotor aspects still have to be further developed while for affective it is good because the curriculum at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu tends to be dominant for religious learning in shaping students' emotional intelligence, especially for students in grade VII MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu.

6.6. The effect of the Radec learning model through learning motivation on improving the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu

The results of testing the sixth hypothesis found that the Radec learning model through learning motivation has a positive and significant effect on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu. The significant effect results show that student learning motivation is able to mediate or be able to increase the influence of the Radec learning model in improving student learning outcomes, so that the Radec learning model as a whole can have a real impact on the process and results of social studies learning in class VII at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu. Learning motivation is an internal drive that encourages students to learn and achieve their academic goals. Learning motivation is not only a determining factor of individual success, but also a mediation that can optimize the effectiveness of the Radec learning model. A high learning motivation will create a dynamic classroom atmosphere, where students not only passively receive information, but are also actively involved in the learning process.

6.7. The influence of school environment through learning motivation on improving the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu

The results of testing the seventh hypothesis found that the school environment through learning motivation has a positive and significant effect on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu. The results of significant influence indicate that student learning motivation is able to mediate or be able to increase the influence of the school environment in improving student learning outcomes, so that the presence of teachers, students, and various learning facilities will provide benefits to the process and results of social studies learning in class VII at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu.

7. Conclusion

The Radec learning model has a positive and significant effect on the learning motivation of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu.

The school environment has a positive and significant effect on the learning motivation of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu. Model pembelajaran Radec berpengaruh positif dan signifikan terhadap hasil belajar siswa kelas VII pada mata pelajaran IPS di MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu.

The school environment has a positive and significant effect on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu..

Learning motivation has a positive and significant effect on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu.

Radec learning model through learning motivation has a positive and significant effect on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu..

The school environment through learning motivation has a positive and significant effect on the learning outcomes of seventh grade students in social studies subjects at MTs Negeri 2 Kotamobagu..

Advice

- Teachers should understand and integrate the Radec learning model in every learning activity and encourage students to actively participate in learning. As well as providing constructive feedback on student performance.
- The Head of Madrasah should encourage the development of teachers' skills related to the application of the Radec model and provide adequate resources in the form of books, software, or laboratory facilities, which support the Radec model.
- The Ministry of Religious Affairs of Kotamobagu City should encourage learning innovations, conduct regular coaching and supervision and create a conducive school environment with adequate facilities and various technical guidance in increasing student motivation and learning outcomes through competitive teacher work progress.
- Students should actively take part in the learning process, continue to develop various understandings and be active to achieve the best grades in social studies.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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